

Factors Affecting the Young Consumers' Intention to Use E-Ticketing Systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka

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Introduction

Background of the Study

The railway is one of the special types of transportation that may have a significant impact on the transportation sector (Jayasuriya and Nimesha, 2022). The train service can be recognized as one of the main & cheapest options used for transportation in Sri Lanka (Destination and Newswire, 2022). E-ticketing refers to the digitized form of tickets that eliminates the need for physical paper, enabling the purchase and issuance of tickets electronically (Soegoto, Setiawan, and Jumansyah, 2020). The railway ticketing system in Sri Lanka is often inefficient (Silva *et al.*, 2019). This is because Sri Lanka's railway system still mainly uses traditional methods. Train stations with few tickets counters waste passengers' time. Office hour queues often result in missed trains. Previous studies show this issue. Additionally, there's no efficient way to access train details before reservations are made. The e-ticketing system is a better way to encourage people to use public transport as well as to solve the problem mentioned above (Jayasuriya, Kathriarachchi, and Vidanagama, 2022). A study on airline electronic ticketing in Jordan has revealed that age is a major factor affecting the use of technologies and younger consumers tend to use modern technologies and applications when booking and purchasing e-ticketing (Al-Dmour *et al.*, 2017). A limited number of studies have been conducted in Sri Lanka on the factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use railway e-ticketing. Therefore, there is a need for further studies to identify factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use

e-ticketing for railway service in Sri Lanka thereby promoting the use of such systems.

Research problem

Earlier research has shown that Sri Lanka now uses an e-ticketing system (Destination and Newswire, 2022; Newswire, 2022; SLT-MOBITEL, 2022). However, it is said that inefficiencies still exist in the Sri Lanka railway service, because railway passengers are not using e-ticketing systems (Silva *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, it has become a necessity to study the factors that affect young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in railway service in Sri Lanka to promote the use of such systems. Although there has been a lot of study on a variety of topics related to the railway service in Sri Lanka, the most of them has been done to create new systems (Kahandawaarachchi, 2019; Silva *et al.*, 2019). At the same time, there are some previous studies related to the railway ticketing system in Sri Lanka and their main purposes are to identify the system features and functions of smart ticketing and reservation in Sri Lanka (Jayasuriya, Kathriarachchi and Vidanagama, 2022). Accordingly, previous studies have given less attention to identifying the factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use the e-ticketing system. Therefore, this research will be conducted to identify the factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use railway e-ticketing, with the motive of fulfilling the above-mentioned research gap.

Research objectives

1. To identify the factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in railway service in Sri Lanka.
2. To find out the relationship between each identified factor and young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in railway service in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

The research adopts a deductive approach, building hypotheses from existing theories. It aims to identify factors affecting consumer's intention to use e-ticketing in Sri Lanka railways. Quantitative research employs a model based on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and previous studies.

Many studies conducted on the use of e-ticketing using the TAM model have used Perceived usefulness (PU), Perceived ease of use (PEOU), Convenience (C), Perceived risk (PR), web security (WS), and trust (T) and it has been revealed in previous studies that these variables influence the customer's intention to use e-ticketing (Dyna and Adi, 2011; Feel, Gee and A, 2012; Sun and Huoi, 2013; Johan *et al.*, 2016; Syarifudin, Abbas and Heriyati, 2019; Puthur, George and Mahadevan, 2020; Tudu, 2020). These six main determinants chosen as the independent variables. Consumer's intention to use E-ticketing system is the dependent variable.

Based on the factors in the previous similar studies, the conceptual model for this study was created as follows (Figure 1).

Figure 2 : Conceptual model

There are six hypotheses checked in this study,

- H1: Perceived usefulness is positively affected to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka
- H2: Perceived ease of use is positively affected to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka
- H3: Convenience is positively affected to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka
- H4: Web security is positively affected to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka
- H5: Perceived risk is positively affected to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka
- H6: Trust is positively related to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka.

The population of the study will be young people (age between 20-28) (Bryden *et al.*, 2001) who use and want to use railway E-ticketing systems in Sri Lanka. The target population for the study is considered to be the undergraduates of Sri Jayewardenepura University located in the Colombo area. Also, a sample of undergraduates from the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce (FMSC), which is the largest faculty of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura is selected based on convenience sampling. According to danielsoper sample calculate minimum sample size is 97 in this study. An online questionnaire, with demographic and Likert scale-based questions, is utilized for data collection. Descriptive analysis summarizes sample characteristics, while regression analysis explores relationships between independent variables (usefulness, ease of use, convenience, web security, risk, and trust) and the dependent variable consumer's intention to use e-ticketing system. Multiple regression is applied due to metric variables. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Smart PLS software are used for data analysis, with hypotheses tested for acceptance. The study aims to provide insights into factors

influencing consumer adoption of e-ticketing in Sri Lanka railways, aiding in the development of more effective systems and services.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Data Analysis of Model Constructs – Preliminary Analysis

Descriptive analysis was performed to calculate the mean values, standard deviation, and Skewness of the models using SPSS software (see Table 4.1). The data distribution for the constructs described that the mean value range varies between 3.8909 and 3.1773. After analysing the data, it was found that for most of the respondents, each question has a Likert scale value of 3 or 4 selected as their response.

Construct	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness
C	1.25	5.00	3.8909	.94731	-1.038
IU	1.00	5.00	3.7818	.97399	-.968
PEOU	1.00	5.00	3.7309	.90480	-.798
PR	1.00	5.00	3.1773	.87219	-.117
PU	1.00	5.00	3.7364	.88740	-.656
T	1.50	5.00	3.6068	.84217	-.286
WS	1.50	4.00	3.2818	.77896	-.184

Table 3 : Descriptive data analysis for model constructs

Reliability and Validity

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Convenience	0.885	0.891	0.743
Intention to use	0.936	0.937	0.796
Perceived ease of use	0.921	0.923	0.761
Perceived risk	0.862	0.864	0.709
Perceived usefulness	0.912	0.914	0.740
Trust	0.878	0.884	0.731
web security	0.890	0.894	0.695

A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher should be present to demonstrate acceptable internal consistency (Taber, 2018). The analysis revealed that the Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.862 to 0.936.

Table 4 : Cronbach's Alpha, CR and AVE values

In this study, it was concluded that Perceived Ease of Use and Trust are important factors in determining customer intention to use railway e-ticketing in Sri Lanka (See table 1).

This study was conducted to answer the two main questions.

1. What are the factors affecting the young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in railway service in Sri Lanka?

A conceptual model was developed based on the review of the literature. Accordingly, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) model was used in this study. In this study, the first objective was achieved through the first

research question. According to the literature review, perceived Ease of Use, Perceived usefulness, Convenience, Web Security Trust, and Perceived Risk were identified in the current study as the factors that strongly affect the consumer's intention to use railway e-ticketing. Therefore, these factors were selected as independent variables and consumers' Intention to use e-ticketing was a dependent variable. Accordingly, in this study, the solution to the first research question was found according to the literature review.

2. What is the relationship between each identified factor and the young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in railway service in Sri Lanka?

Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 5 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.813 ^a	0.660	0.640	0.583	1.827

- a. Predictors: (Constant), PEOU, PR, WS, C, PU, T
- b. b. Dependent Variable: IU

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	68.283	6	11.380	33.377	<.001 ^b
Residual	35.119	103	0.340		
Total	103.403	109			

a. Dependent Variable: IU

b. Predictors: (Constant), PEOU, PR, WS, C, PU, T

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Consultant)	0.040	0.292		0.136	0.892
C	0.023	0.108	0.023	0.217	0.829
PR	0.042	0.089	0.038	0.473	0.638
WS	0.067	0.106	0.053	0.629	0.531
PU	0.034	0.111	0.031	0.303	0.763
T	0.445	0.126	0.385	3.537	0.001
PEOU	0.420	0.108	0.390	3.888	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: EFS

*Significance at $p < 0.05$

This study was conducted to determine factors can affect the young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing system in railway service in Sri

Lanka. It hypothesized that young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing will be predicted by the Convenience, Perceived Risk, Web Security, Perceived Usefulness, Trust, and Perceived Ease of Use. Multiple Regression Analysis is used to test the hypothesis. To evaluate the hypothesis, a multiple regression analysis was conducted, results reveal that 58.3% of the variance in Consumers' intention can be explained by the six predictors, collectively, $F(6,100) = 33.377$, $p < 0.001$ as per table 3. The results show that the Trust ($\beta = 0.385$, $t = 3.537$, $p < 0.001$), and Perceive Ease of Use ($\beta = 0.390$, $t = 3.888$, $p = 0.000$) positively predict Consumers' intention to use when considering the individual contributions of the predictors. This suggests that Sri Lankan Youth are most concerned about Trust and Perceived Ease of Use in railway e-ticketing.

Hypotheses Testing

Path coefficient values in a theoretical model represent the strength and direction of the relationships between variables. In hypothesis testing, the significance of each construct was evaluated using a bootstrapping procedure at a confidence level of 95% ($p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient (β)	Statistics (T)	P Value	Outcome
H1	0.026	0.259	0.398	Not supported
H2	0.411	3.383	0.000	Supported
H3	0.077	0.847	0.199	Not Supported
H4	0.105	0.957	0.169	Not Supported
H5	-0.049	0.463	0.322	Not Supported
H6	0.348	2.895	0.002	Supported

Table 6 : Results of Structural Model analysis

H1 suggested that Perceived usefulness is positively affect to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka. However, due to the non-significance of Perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.026$, $p = 0.398$), H1 was not supported. H2 postulated that Perceived ease of use is positively affect to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service. H2 was also not supported. Because

Due to the non-significance of Subjective Norms ($\beta= 0.411$, $p=0.000$). Convenience ($\beta= 0.077$, $p= 0.199$) and web security ($\beta= 0.105$, $p= 0.169$) are also found as statistically not significant and has not a positively affect to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka, not supporting H3 and H4. It revealed that Perceived risk ($\beta= -0.049$, $p= 0.322$) is statistically not significant and has not a positively affect to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka, not supporting H5. Moreover, H6 was supported due to the statistical significance of Trust ($\beta= 0.348$, $p= 0.002$) It also revealed that Trust is positively affect to the young consumer's intention to use E-ticketing systems in Railway Service in Sri Lanka.

Discussion

According to the results of the analysis, some of the hypotheses of the study were supported and some of the hypotheses were not supported.

Perceived ease of use significantly affects young consumers' intention to use E-ticketing in Sri Lanka's Railway Service. Previous studies also support this (Sulaiman, Ng and Mohezar, 2008; Dyna and Adi, 2011; Feel, Gee and A, 2012), and respondents found the system user-friendly.

Trust significantly impacts young consumers' intention to use E-ticketing in Sri Lanka's Railway Service, consistent with prior research (Dyna and Adi, 2011; Sun and Huoi, 2013; Bukhari, 2014). Respondents' willingness to accept vulnerability in e-ticket purchases stems from positive expectations for future behaviour.

According to the results of the path model analysis, four of the hypotheses of the study were not supported.

Perceived usefulness does not positively affect young customers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in Sri Lanka Railways, contrary to previous studies (Dyna and Adi, 2011; Feel, Gee and A, 2012; Sun and Huoi, 2013; Bukhari, 2014). Respondents do not believe it enhances their performance.

Convenience does not positively affect young customers' intention to use e-ticketing in Sri Lanka Railways. Previous studies show mixed results (Feel, Gee and A, 2012; Johan *et al.*, 2016), possibly due to respondents' familiarity with existing ticketing methods.

Web security does not positively affect young customers' intention to use e-ticketing in Sri Lanka Railways, contrary to some prior studies (Feel, Gee and A, 2012; Sun and Huoi, 2013; Johan *et al.*, 2016).

Perceived risk was not found to positively affect young customers' intention to use e-ticketing systems in Sri Lanka Railways, contrary to previous studies. This contradicts the established relationship between perceived risk and consumer intention in e-ticketing system usage (Dyna and Adi, 2011; Feel, Gee and A, 2012; Sun and Huoi, 2013). Consequently, hypotheses H1, H3, H4, and H5 were not supported, while H2 and H6 were supported at a 95% confidence level.

Conclusion

This study conducted to identify factors and relationship between each identified factor and affecting the young consumers' intention to use e-ticketing for railway service in Sri Lanka. According to multiple regression analysis, four hypotheses (H1, H3, H4, and H6) were not supported and two hypotheses (H2 and H5) were supported.

This study enriches the TAM model, demonstrating its effectiveness in assessing factors affecting the consumer's adoption of railway e-ticketing. It highlights Perceived Ease of Use and Trust as crucial factors, reducing knowledge gaps in Sri Lanka railway e-ticketing. The findings have broad applicability in e-ticketing development across transport sectors, offering insights for system enhancement and policy formulation. Limitations include small sample size (limited to FMSC undergraduates), exclusive focus on youth, and cross-sectional design hindering causality determination. Time constraints also affected study duration. Advocate for future longitudinal studies to delve deeper into factors influencing consumer intention for railway e-ticketing.

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